

A comparative Study of the Anxiety and Aggression among the female volleyball players of Kashmir Province

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Abstract

The volleyball game was invented more as a recreational game rather than anything else involving more people. The results of the present study will help to identify anxiety and aggression of sports woman representing university in team and individual events. This will further help to identify sportswomen who may have potential to be of high calibre. Competitive sports are full of challenges, so youngsters taken to competitive sports must display the required psychological attributes including aggression, anxiety and emotional intelligence to meet the challenges successfully. The skill involved in the game are of simple, natural and highly stimulating and satisfying to anyone who participates in the game. This study assumes significance in view of the anxiety and aggression among the team and individual sportsmen of Kashmir province. It has been suggested that team and individual sportsmen with respect of findings of the present study there are clear linkages of the variables of perceived impact of life changes. The finding also suggested that on anxiety and aggression individual sportsmen were high on mean scores. The two variables anxiety and aggression have a significant difference at two levels finding the significant difference but differ on mean scores. These finding can lead to indigenous intervention package for coaches belonging to University teams. Research evidence revealed the level of anxiety and aggression among team and individual sportsmen.

Keywords: Anxiety; Aggression; Volleyball

1. Introduction

Volleyball has become very popular all over the world. Almost all the nations play this game for enjoyment and competitions. The volleyball game was invented more as a recreational game rather than anything else involving more people. At first, volleyball was used without a net throwing the ball from one group to another. During the past couple of decades the game has drastically changed in its nature and it has taken a different shape as we see today. At present volleyball has also got its modified/changed version which is more popularly known as Beach Volleyball. Both the version of game requires high demands of physical, physiological and psychological qualities to compete and excel at the national and international level. However, the modern volleyball is the game which calls for strenuous continuous thrilling action. The skill involved in the game are of simple, natural and highly stimulating and satisfying to anyone who participates in the game.

The skill includes diving, spiking, blocking etc. which are demands of modern volleyball. Aggression and aggressiveness have several different meanings in everyday speech - the actions of a brutal slayer or a successful salesperson - are we talking about the same thing? Aggression is any form of behaviour directed toward the goal of harming or injuring another living being who is motivated to avoid such harm. Anxiety is a natural human reaction that involves mind and body. It serves an important basic survival function: Anxiety is an alarm system that is activated whenever a person perceives danger or threat. When the body and mind react to danger or threat, a person feels physical sensations of anxiety - things like a faster heartbeat and breathing, tense muscles, sweaty palms, a queasy stomach, and trembling hands or legs. These sensations are part of the body's fight flight response. They are caused by a rush of adrenaline and other chemicals that prepare the body to make a quick getaway from danger. The fight-flight response happens instantly when a person senses a threat. It takes a few seconds longer for the thinking part of the brain (the cortex) to process the situation and evaluate whether the threat is real, and if so, how to handle it. If the cortex sends the all-clear signal, the fight-flight response is deactivated and the nervous system can relax.

Anxiety is a negative emotional state in which feeling of nervousness, worry, and apprehension is associated with activation or arousal of the body.”(Robert S Weinberg & Daniel Gould, 2007). State anxiety on be considered to be more situational in nature and is often associated with arousal of the autonomic nervous system that anxiety can be thought of as a

world view that an individual uses when coping with situation in his or her environment (Spielberger,1966). Researchers based found that, Competitive state anxiety is higher for amateur athletes in individual sports compared with athletes in team sports (Simon & Martens. 1977). Studied the anxiety and performance in selected non-professional athletes and result suggest that there was a significantly negative correlation between anxiety scores and performance on the irritability, depression & anxiety questionnaire Hannon, B. & Fitzgerald, P. (2006). Our ability to obtain independent measure of cognitive and somatic state anxiety has greatly enhanced our knowledge about the athletic situation. One of the factors that are believed to significantly influence the qualities of the athletic experience is the level of state anxiety during the time leading up to competition. Pre competitive anxiety starts relatively high and remains high and stable as the time of the event approaches. (Richard H. Cox -2007).

The results of the present study will help to identify anxiety and aggression of sports woman representing university in team and individual events. This will further help to identify sportswomen who may have potential to be of high calibre. Competitive sports are full of challenges, so youngsters taken to competitive sports must display the required psychological attributes including aggression, anxiety and emotional intelligence to meet the challenges successfully. The variables anxiety and aggression need to be studied properly, both from the theoretical and practical point of view. The knowledge about the variables may enable the teacher and coaches to takes decisions in their work with young players taking part at different levels and train them in a proper way. The investigation can help the University coaches who are attached with University camps to find out the talent and how to wide out them so as to enable them to perform better in future in the teams and individual games and find out the weakness of the sportsmen who are attending the coaching camps.

2. Methodology

The present study is based on descriptive in nature. Research methodology is based on the following parameters. The detailed description is of the research methodology is elaborated as below. This study has been under taken to assess and evaluate Anxiety and among the female players belonging to team and individual sports events. For this purpose, the procedure adopted for selection of subjects, Selection of variables, selection of test, description of tests,

administration of questionnaire, collection of data, method of scoring and “statistical design utilized has been described in detail.

For the purpose of this study 60 female Volleyball players were selected as subjects. The subjects were of two levels i.e. District level and state level. Equal numbers of subjects were randomly selected. The sample was collected from different degree colleges of valley.

Description of tool

Anxiety Scale

Ours is said to be the age of anxiety. Anxiety is a common symptom which is found almost every individual of the worked and especially in students of today. Anxiety can be defined as a ‘stage of arousal’ caused by threat to well being (Spielberger, 1960). ‘State’ means a condition involving the entire organism. ‘Arousal’ means a condition of tension, unrest or uneasiness, or a readiness to act the respond. ‘Threat’ means anticipation of pain or danger or serious interference with foal seeking activities. Operationally, anxiety can be defines as the automatic response pattern characteristic of a particular individual organism after the administration of a noxious stimulus (Wolpe, 1952).

Anxiety is one of the most important problems in Psychology. The investigations of ‘Manifest Anxiety’ began at the Iowa University by Spence and Taylor (1951, 1953, 1956). The research starts with a set of items from MMPI (Minnesota Multiphase Personality Inventory), first appeared in 1940 and the manual in 1943 which have been judged to be indicative of overt anxiety symptoms (Taylor, 1951). Taylor revised her inventory ‘A Personality Scale of Manifest Anxiety’ in 1953. These items together, with other buffer items, are used to constitute a scale which is administered to introductory psychology students. The top and bottom 10-20% are selected and designated as high and low MAS subjects. Taylor’s manifest anxiety scale provides a quick and reliable measure of anxiety as assessed by the Rorschach Test (Eichler, 1951). No doubt that these Iowa University investigations stimulated a large volume of research on anxiety and its correlates.

Sarason and mandler have developed their anxiety questionnaire “Test Anxiety Questionnaire”, in 1952. In 1957, Cattell introduced his IPAT anxiety scale and in 1959, Martin developed a test on anxiety. Jenkins and Lykken (1957) have pointed out that in some cases high

MAS subjects may show better performance than low AMAS subjects on the first conditioning trial i.e., before the CS and the US have paired. Standish and Champion (1960) confirmed that the higher MAS subjects did relatively better than low MAS Subjects on the simple task but his relationship was reversed with the difficult material. It was shown in many studies (Sinha, D., 1958, 1961, 1966, 1966) in India that anxiety is related to academic attainment and performances. In one study academic ranks and the correlation of the anxiety score was found to be significant at .01 levels (Sinha, D., 1961). In India, anxiety scale construction starts with the work of S.D. Kapoor of Delhi. His test was published as hindi adaptation of Cattell's IPAT. 'Sinha W-A Self-Analysis Form' a anxiety test in Hindi by Prof. D. Sinha of Allahabad was published 1966. A Hindi adaptation of Taylor's Anxiety Scale was developed in 1967 by B.N. Singh and R.C. Thakur of Muzzaffernagar. 'Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety Test' by A.K. P. Sinha of Delhi and L.N.K. Sinha of Patna was published in 1973.

Development of the Test:

The anxiety Scale has been developed for use with school and college students of India. The preliminary form of the test has 150 'Yes-No' type items on the following areas: (1) Psychological manifestations, (2) Ambition, (3) Future, (4) Family, (5) Relations, (6) Friendship, (7) Love, (8) Health, Virtue & War, (10) Shame, and (11) Guilt. In the item-construction help was taken from most of the tests mentioned in the introduction of this manual.

After giving proper instructions to the subject of the sample the preliminary test was administrated. Their age range was 1q6-24 years. After calculating the number of examinees doing each item correctly as well as incorrectly, use of extreme groups as described by Anastasi (1968) was followed. Item-analysis was done with the help of the method described by Anastasi (1968). 120 items were of good discriminative value, so 20 items were eliminated. In the final test there are 100 'Yes-No' type of items. It has been prepared both in Hindi and English. Ordinarily and examinee takes about 20 to 25 mionutes time in answering the test.

RELIABILITY: The coefficient of reliability was determined by split-half method and test-retest method. The test-retest reliability was determined by administrating the test after two weeks time. The following shows the reliability coefficients determined by above two methods:

Table 1: Showing Reliability of the Test.

Method	Sample	N	Reliability Coefficients
Split-Half	Male	200	.93
Test-retest	Male	83	.91

VALIDITY: The validation criterion used for this test was to correlate the scores of this present test with scores of other valid test on manifest anxiety in Hindi. For these following two tests were selected:

- (1) Sinha W-A Self-Analysis from constructed and standardized by Prof. D. Sinha again on 100 male subjects correlation was found to be .73.
- (2) Sinha's comprehensive Anxiety test constructed by A.K. P. Sinha and L.N.L. Sinha on 100 male subject's correlation was found to .71.

ADMINISTRATION OF THE TEST

It is a self-administering inventory. The examiner should read the instructions given on the cover page of the inventory before the instructions silently along with the examinee. There is no time limit for the test. Ordinarily an examinee takes about 20 to 25 minutes time in completing the whole inventory. The examinees should interpret the questions himself. The questions regarding the meaning or contents, if any, should be answered by the examiner.

The examiner should make every effort to secure the frank and sincere co-operation of the examinees. The examiner may assure the examinees that the results would always remain strictly confidential. Questions from examinees concerning the purpose and use of the inventory should be answered frankly.

Scoring Uses of the Test

The inventory can be scored accurately by hand in three or four minutes of time. For any answer checked as 'Yes' should be given the score of one. The total manifest anxiety score of every examinee would be the sum of items checked as 'Yes'. The present test is a measure of manifest anxiety and is useful for group administration. Like other tests of manifest anxiety this test can also be used in research and survey purposes. With the help of this test one can screen easily high or low manifest anxiety score subjects.

NORMS: Percentile norms for the present inventory are given in Table-2 Number of units in the sample were 471 male and 502 were female reading in graduate and post-graduate classes. Percentile norms were calculated for males and females and are given separately in Table-2. The subject can be classified into five categories on the basis of scores obtained on the inventory. The five categories are: 'A+' stands for very high anxiety, 'B' stands for normal range anxiety, 'C' stands for low anxiety and, 'C—' stands for very low level of anxiety.

AGGRESSION SCALE

The term 'aggression' is a mode of Frustration (Chauhan and Tiwari, 1971). "Frustration is a state of affairs against which the effected individual's energies are more or less strongly mobilized which he seeks to culminate, or, if possible entirely to avoid, if happiness may fairly be said to represent the ultimate goal of all human endeavour, frustration as its its-thesis." (Mowser, 1938). According to Krech and Crutchfield (1962). "Frustration is the motivational and emotional state which results from persistent of blockage of goal-directed behaviour. It may lead the individual change in cognition to maladaptive behaviour." Aggression has been considered as a defence mechanism in Abnormal Psychology whereas in general, aggression is a normal behaviour and in daily life. We can see the aggression behaviour of all type of individuals. Freud emphasis the study of aggression to understand human behaviour disorders. For Freud, aggression is one of the consequences of frustration. This suggestion of Freud is widely accepted by Dollard, Miller, Doob, Mowrer and Sears (Called as Yale group) who formulated a wellknown theory of Aggression, in which they stated that frustration results in aggression (Weller and /suleman, 1968). Aggression has been defined as "an act whose goal responses are injury an organism or organism-surrogate" (Dollard et. al., 1939).

“Aggression may be defined operationally in terms of made answering to Enders frequent quarrelling’s, broken engagement, impulses of take revenge and reactionary attitudes to traditions and beliefs”. (Chauhan and Tiwari, 1972). Yale group hypotheses of ‘Frustration’ ‘Aggression’ formally advanced by Millar Dollard (1941) and they defined aggressive behaviour is a logical and expected consequence of frustration. They state that when our efferets relate to the goal directed behavior suffers interference our first reaction is often one if attacking and attempting to remove the obstacle. So aggression in behaviour follows aggression. Researches of Postne (1952) and Lazares (1966) has shown, “ that this is particularly likely to be or reactionwhen the obstacle is viewed as arbitrarily imposed”. According to Filler (1952) the yale group theory of frustration, “Aggression asserts the occurrence of aggression always forms of aggression. “Yale group takes aggression in a very broad sense which is difficult to hold. Later on, in a research paper, Doob and Sears (1939) modified this position by saying, “all frustrating situations do not produce overt aggression is immediately evident” In 1411 Millar accepted the modification made by Doob and Sears (1939) and Sears (1948) and gives his explanation as, “Frustration produces, instigations to a number of different types of response, one of which is an instigations to some form of aggression”. The followers of frustration aggression hypotheses do not accept that the behaviour instigated by motivation. They believe both types of behaviour are means to an end and punishment is regarded as method for inhibiting both types of behaviours.

Hovlang and Sears (1940) studied the relationship between total lurching (aggression) and index of economic activity (Frustration) and supported the theory of frustration-aggression hypothesis.

The findings of Holland and Sperry (1951) suggest that highly frustrated children are more aggressive. Whiting (1944) who conducted an anthropoigical study of Kwoma and found that the aggression is the only type of reaction to frustration.

Portage (1952) proposes an important modification in frustration-aggression theory. The proposes a response-inhibition hypotheses which was confirmed by Rathans and Worchal (1960). Por are found significantly greater number of aggressive e responses in the arbitrary (unreasonable) than in the Non-Arbitrary (reasonable) situations. Krogarman and Werchal (1961) studies to verify this hypothesis and notes the effects of expectation and reasonableness’ increase the expression of aggression towards the self and reduce the tendency to express

aggression towards the frustrator. Cohen (1955) introduces two more variables which are relevant to the frustration aggression hypothesis. These two variables are Idea actual (Arbitrariness Non Arbitrariness of Postore) and authority-poor. Cohen from his study concludes that less aggression under 'Ideal' behaviour, less aggression in 'non arbitrary' (reasonable) situations, less aggression where frustrator is an 'Authority figure'.

Freud and his associates believe that the aggression is an universal outcome of the "thantos and that aagression aderire to destroy was the natural Energy emerging from Thantos instinct (Death Instinct)". Fromm, Horney. Allport and Maslow have also supported this view of aggression as an inevitable element in the make up of human personality.

In this context (Frustration-aggression hypothesis) McClelland (1945) has also done significant work. He created situation of fruistration in the laboratory. He puts his findings in er own words as far as present data are concerned and aggressive responses, if defined rigidly as responses directed at attacking the frustrating onject or a substitute directed frojrn only around 13 percent of the total number of responses under conditions in which the anticipation of punishment is reduced to a minimum.

Frustration results in aggression (Weller and Suleman, 1958) and aggression results where punishment is inflicted (Sears, 1961). Aft5er infancy social folerence for aggressionness of children gets diminished (Whitney, 1953). Aggression and phantasy remain positively related (Mussen, Mayer-1954), Overt motor verbal expression of aggression are inhibited by punishment or retaliation with the result that indirect or converts outlets get started (Anusubel 1957). Threats or attacks upon the 'Self' produce aggressive tendencies..

As pointed out earlier, Dollard, Doob, Miller, Menser and Sears have made a close and strong relationship between frustration and aggression and formulated the frustration –aggression hypotheses. Whenever goal directed behaviour sutters interference frustration results and aggression in behaviour follows this frustration. The proponents of frustration-aggression hypotheses believe that the behaviour instigated by frustration and behaviour elicited by motivation are the same. They regard both types of behaviour are a mebas to an end and punishment in regarded as a method for inhibiting both ttypes of behaviour (Maiyer, 1949). In 1962 Borkowitz have suggested the revised theory of frustration aggression hypothesis.

STANDARDIZATION OF THE SCALE

Selection of the item:

The items of the scale have been selected on the basis of literature and the judgement of experts (including Psychologists and Clinical practitioners). All the items of the scale are presented in simple and brisk style. Some of the items have been taken from well used as well as well standardized Frustration Scale by Chauhan and Tiwari (1971).

The Scale Format:

On the basis of available literature review and related existing tools, the preliminary scale of Aggression was prepared which consisted 70 items. The present scale is based on Chauhan and Tiwari's frustration scale or it can be said that the present scale is the extended form of Chauhan and Tiwari's Frustration scale in which aggression has been taken as a mode of frustration. These items were related to reactionary attitudes to traditions, irritation, drive for dominance, love for fighting, story retaliation, anger behaviour, aggressive tendency against existing rude traditional social customs and rules, preference for fighters and for counter behaviour, appreciation for rebellion and competitiveness. The preliminary form of the scale was given to 15 judges (including Psychologists, Social workers and Psychiatrists) with the request to rate each item on five point scale (Most Appropriate to Least Appropriate), according to the concept of aggression, language of items and its clearness of meaning. Thus only, those items were retained in the final form of the scale which possess most appropriateness as assessed by the experts. So, final form of the scale has 30 items. So we can say all the items of this five scale are presented in simple and brisk style. Each of the item has five alternate answers (multiple choice) graded on five negative dimension. Operationally defined, all the items of this Aggression scale are matter of behaviour in daily life. They are thus immediately meaningful and interesting. There is no obscurity or complexity in items.

Instructions:

Simple instructions are printed on the front page of the test. It is essential for the tester to read the instructions and if testee feel any difficulty than he must remove all the queries of the testee. The standard instructions are __

1. "Some questions along with there altenated answers are given in next pages.
2. Read each question carefully also read the accompanying answers attentively. Make your choice for the best answers out of the several alternative answers and put a 'tick mark' in brackets (✓).
3. Before putting the tick mark, please read the question and the accompanying answers very carefully.
4. There Is no time limit for your answers but try to finish whole test as early as possible. Please do not leave any questions.
5. You are to make a tick for only one reply and you have to select only one response for one question out of several alternative e answers.
6. Your answers will be kept confidential so you are free to give your answers in your own way.
7. Now please start your work and finish the work as early as possible.

Reliability of the Scale:

For getting the reliability co-efficient, the scale was administered to 300subjects both male and female belonging to rural as well as urban localities of Agra(Age range- 14 to 24 yrs.). the split –half reliability has been calculated by odd-even method. The corelation coefficient was .82 which show the scale is highly reliable.

The test-retest reliability of this scale has also been calculated by administration twiceley of this scale on a sample of 200 subjects (not included in above sample). The reliability coefficient was .78

The Validity of the Scale:

The validity of the scale has been calculated by two methods. For the contant validity because the items of the scale has been collected through the expert's opinions and available literature. So, we can say the test is valid for the measurement of aggression of 14 to 24 yrs. Of age group.

The validity of this scale again checked through the administration of both, present scale and Chauhan and Tiwari's Frustration (only aggressions scores was calculated) with an

interval of 15 days to a sample of 100 students (not include in above sample). The validity coefficient was .74 which show the present scale is valid for the measurement of aggression.

The present scale is available in Hindi and English. To check the both form reliability, both version of the scale was administered to a group of 100 students who know both the languages (i.e Hindi and English). The validity coefficient of the both test was .78 which show the Hindi as well as English version of the scale is valid for measure aggression.

3. Results

The objectives of the present study were to study and compare the level of anxiety and aggression among team and individual sportswomen. To achieve this objective, a sample of 60 sportswomen was taken from different backgrounds. The data on the selective variables was calculated using appropriate tools. The data thus obtained on the two variables was tabulated separately for two groups of sportswomen and was analysed in the manners described below.

COMPARISON OF SPORTSWOMEN REPRESENTING KASHMIR PROVINCE ON DIFFERENT VARIABLES USING 'T'-TEST

One of the objectives of the present study was to compare sportswomen representing university in Individual and Team Events in respect to their means on the variables of Aggression and Anxiety. To serve this purpose, the use of t-test was made. The result of t-test in respects of the two is as under.

COMPARISON OF SPORTSWOMEN REPRESENTING KASHMIR PROVINCE ON THE VARIABLE AGGRESSION USING 't'-test

TABLE.1

	MEAN	SD	DOF	t-VALUE	REMARKS
STATE	79.03	22.39	58	9.36	0.01
DISTRICT	35.1	12.611			

A perusal of the table.1 indicated that there is a significant difference among volleyball female players belonging to Kashmir province from different backgrounds on the variable of

aggression. The t-value crosses the significant value at 0.01 and the calculate value is more that the tabulated value and therefore the first null hypothesis stands rejected.

ANXIETY

COMPARISON OF SPORTSWOMEN REPRESENTING KASHMIR PROVINCE ON THE VARIABLE AGGRESSION Using'-test

Table.2

	MEAN	SD	DOF	t-VALUE	REMARKS
STATE	50.20	11.71	58	6.31	0.01
DISTRICT	32.17	10.39			

A perusal of the table.2 indicated that there is a significant difference among volleyball female players belonging to Kashmir province from different backgrounds on the variable of anxiety. The t-value crosses the significant value at 0.01 and the calculated value is more that the tabulated value and therefore the second null hypothesis stand also rejected

4. Discussion

The findings of the present study have obvious applied implications for physical education and sports in our country. Sportsmen /women, participating in various categories of sports activities, express significant variations in their psyche. Sport participation helps in increasing the crystallized adjustment and managed anxiety, aggression and emotional intelligence that further contribute to better performance. Anxiety, Aggression and Emotional Intelligence are highly related to performance in sports and games. Anxiety and Aggressiveness contribute to increment in sports capacity in one category of games while the same may not help or moderate quantity of anxiety, aggression and emotional intelligence are essential for sportsmen/women irrespective of their participation in varied and sometimes opposing sports categories. This study assumes significance in view of the anxiety and aggression among the team and individual sportsmen of Kashmir province. It has been suggested that team and individual sportsmen with respect of findings of the present study there are clear linkages of the variables of perceived impact of life changes. The finding also suggested that on anxiety and

aggression individual sportsmen were high on mean scores. The two variables anxiety and aggression have a significant difference at two levels finding the significant difference but differ on mean scores. These finding can lead to indigenous intervention package for coaches belonging to University teams. Research evidence revealed the level of anxiety and aggression among team and individual sportsmen.

If people sports are surveyed and asked to identify the characteristics of successful athletes, anxiety, aggression and emotional intelligence would be high on the list in sports; anxieties, aggressive and emotional behaviour have positive meaning in popular culture. The successful athlete is often described as one who is hungry, anxious, aggressive, and emotional, competitor on the other hand. Teacher often describe trouble making or destructive students as anxious, aggressive, and emotional. But such behaviour in athletes is demanded by coaches; it may be discouraged in students and be prohibited by teachers. The last decade has evidenced renewed interest in the phenomenon of anxieties, aggressive emotional intelligence in sports. Anxieties, aggressive and emotional intelligence in sports have been investigated by many scholars from different fields of behavioural science. Keeping in view the determining role of anxieties, aggressiveness and emotional behaviour in competitive performance, the investigator decided to undertake this study at the state and district level. The investigator is of the opinion that such a study would not only reveal the phenomenon of anxiety, aggression and emotional intelligence but also enable us to make overall assessments of district and state level with respect to variables like anxieties and aggression. To Summarise, sixty (60) volley ball female players of various colleges has been taken the subjects for every variables who have represented either at district and state level of Kashmir province. The results of the present study will help to identify anxiety and aggression of sportswomen representing at district and state level.

This will further help to identify sportswomen who may have potential to be of high calibre. Competitive sports are full of challenges, so youngsters taken to competitive sports must display the required psychological attributes including aggression, anxiety and emotional intelligence to meet the challenges successfully. The variables anxiety and aggression need to be studied properly, both from the theoretical and practical point of view. The knowledge about the variables may enable the teacher and coaches to takes decisions in their work with young players taking part at different levels and train them in a proper way. The investigation can help the

University coaches who are attached with University camps to find out the talent and how to wide out them so as to enable them to perform better in future in the teams and individual games and find out the weakness of the sportsmen who are attending the coaching camps.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The scores on Anxiety for the sportswomen representing university in team events were spread over and the mean and standard deviation for the scores on Anxiety at state level came out to be 50.20 and 11.71 at district level 32.17 and 10.39 respectively. Group Level of Anxiety No. of Sportsmen 1 Extremely High Anxiety 8 2 High Anxiety 7 3 Normal Anxiety Level 14 4 Low Anxiety 4 5 Extremely low Anxiety 10 Total 43. The scores on aggression for the sportswomen representing Kashmir province were spread over and the mean and standard deviation for the scores on Aggression came out to be 79.03 and 22.39 and 35.10 and 12.61 at state and district level respectively. Further reveals that the scores on anxiety among sportswomen representing university at district level were not concentrated over a specific scores range. Rather the scores were more or less evenly distributed in all the class intervals. On comparing the scores with the norms given in the manual of the test, the sportswomen representing different levels were grouped on the basis of anxiety as under. Group Level of Anxiety No. of Sportsmen 1 Extremely High Anxiety 14 2 High Anxiety 5 3 Normal Anxiety Level 12 4 Low Anxiety 2 5 Extremely low Anxiety 10 Total 43.

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